

THE ROLE OF TALENT IN FORMING THE INTELLECTUAL CAPABILITIES OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract: In the development of the intellectual potential of preschool children, the role of their innate abilities and talents is important, because our children who have innate abilities quickly learn all the educational, educational and professional teachings of adults. they get it and quickly learn it and apply it to life. This article talks about the role of talent and scientific-psychological considerations in the formation of intellectual abilities in preschool children.

Key words: Preschool age period, intellectual development, talent, ability, children, social environment, educator, psychologist, logical thinking.

Introduction: Today, the development of the intellectual potential of preschoolers is one of the urgent issues. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, said, "Preschool education is the foundation of our tomorrow." In the development of the intellectual potential of preschool children, the role of their innate abilities and talents is important. But not all children have this ability and talent. Therefore, it is primarily the responsibility of our pedagogues and the general public, i.e., families, neighborhoods, educational institutions and managers of enterprises, organizations, and workshops, to develop abilities and improve children's talents. The main content of the concept of talent also means the concept of "ability". In our opinion, the concept of "ability" used in practice has three main parts:

First of all, ability is psychological, it has unique characteristics, it is

understood as an ability that distinguishes one person from another, no one uses this expression when talking about the ability that is common to all people.

Secondly, the term ability is generally used to refer to a person who is dependent on his or her success in performing various activities, rather than referring to any different characteristics inherent in a person. For example, some people undoubtedly have their own qualities: characteristics such as squeamishness, laziness, and laziness cannot usually be called abilities, because it is not always possible to achieve success in any activity.

Thirdly, the concept of "ability" is not determined by some individuals, that is, by their knowledge or lack of knowledge. Often, the pedagogue is not very satisfied with the children's performance, but nevertheless, the child who is not learning well makes the teacher happy with the fact that he tries to master the subjects well without falling behind his peers. The pedagogue bases his displeasure on the fact that he does not deal with children enough, and comes to the conclusion that if he pays attention to the children's abilities and deals with them more, they have the ability to absorb knowledge well..

We cannot understand ability as the natural capabilities of a person, because we defined ability as "the unique psychological characteristics of each person", so it is absolutely impossible to conclude that it is a natural characteristic that exists in any person. Natural can only be anatomico-physiological features, i.e., a talent based on the development of ability, the ability itself appears as a result of continuous development.

Literature analysis and methodology.

Ability is one of the most important features of the human psyche, and due to the possibility of filling these features excessively, the relative weakness of some ability even makes it impossible to successfully perform activities related to this ability. it's not. A lack of ability in one person can be a boundary between another person.

The possibility of covering the border is different: for example, musical talent and an activity related to music or a similar field; in the absence of talent, any attempt will inevitably lead to failure..

"Talent" and "ability" have their own characteristic concepts, in which human characteristics are seen in terms of the requirements presented by any practical activity. Therefore, it is possible to talk about talent in general. Talent is said only in relation to something, some kind of activity. This is especially important when considering the question of "general talent". It is the interdependence of specific practical activities within the concept of "talent" that defines the historical character of this concept. The concept of "talent" loses its meaning when it is considered a biological characteristic. Talent, as we understand it, is included in any one or another type of activity and, without a doubt, is seriously dependent on the "successful" performance of each specific activity..

It should be noted that ability is a dynamic concept with its existence. Ability appears only in action, only in development. Psychologically, it is impossible to talk about ability as it exists before its development, and about the ability to stop developing when it reaches its full development. Because the ability must be in constant development. From this it can be concluded that ability does not appear outside of specific activities. Only we can distinguish them from each other by psychological analysis. It is impossible to conclude that the ability exists before the start of a specific activity and is used only at its end. An infant's absolute hearing ability does not exist before pitch awareness is first born. Until then, there was only a badge of talent like anatomy-physiological reality. It is not a matter of ability being manifested in activity, but of their creation in this activity. The development of ability, and any development in general, is not simple, its driving force is to deal with contradictions, therefore, at any stage of development, there may be conflicts between abilities and interests. However,

recognizing such conflicts that may be , the emergence and development of interests appear independently of ability.

In conclusion, it can be said that we do not accept the concept of ability as a natural characteristic of a person, but in many cases, based on the development of ability, we can see that some people have a natural characteristic, that is, talent. Sometimes the concept of "natural" is connected with the concept of ability in practical analysis when it is said with words like "real", "natural", "given by nature" and so on. In most cases, we understand naturalness as the ability underlying the development of talent.

References:

1. Askarov, A. (2022). CREATIVE THINKING IN PRESCHOOL SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPMENT. *Science and innovation*, 1(B8), 87-91.
2. Rahimjon o'g'li, A. A. (2022). Maktabgacha Yoshdagi Bolalarning Aqliy Taraqqiyotining Rivojlanishida O 'Yin Rivojlantiruvchi Faoliyat Sifatida. *Uzbek Scholar Journal*, 5, 207-209.
3. Asqarov, A. (2022). Maktabgacha Yosh Davrda Kreativ Tafakkurni Rivojlanishining Ijtimoiy Psixologik Aspektlari. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 2(6), 882-883.
4. O'G'Li, A. A. R. (2022). XOTIRANI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING O'ZIGA XOS USULLARI. *Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali*, 1(6).
5. Kamilova, F. X. (2023). MAKTABGACHA YOSH DAVRDA MANTIQUIY VA KREATIV TAFAKKUR RIVOJLANISHINING IJTIMOIIY PSIXOLOGIK MEXANIZMLARI VA ASPEKTLARI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(5), 508-512.

6. o'g'li Asqarov, A. R., & Turdimatov, J. (2023). KEKSALIK DAVRIDA XOTIRA JARAYONINING O 'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARINI PSIXOLOGIK ASOSLARI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(5), 513-516.
7. o'g'li Asqarov, A. R., & Turdimatova, E. (2023). MANTIQUIY TAFAKKURNI RIVOJLANTIRISH USULLARI. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(5), 482-485.
8. o'g'li Asqarov, A. R., & Musayev, J. (2023). TA'LIM MUHITIDA O'QUVCHI SHAXSI XAVFSIZLIGIGA TAXDIDLAR VA ULARNI BARTARAF QILISHNING IJTIMOIIY-PSIXOLOGIK USULLARI. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(15), 254-258.
9. Rahimjon o'g'li, A. A., & Baxtiyorovna, M. S. (2023). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNING INTELLEKTUAL QOBILIYATLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA ISTE'DODNING O'RNI. *IQRO*, 3(1), 314-316.
10. Zaylobidin o'g'li, A. I. (2023). KICHIK MAKTAB YOSHDAGI O'QUVCHILARDA O'Z-O'ZINI ANGLASHDA IJTIMOIIYLASHUVNI O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(12), 94-98.
11. Ibroximjonovna, N. T. (2023). THE PROBLEM ANALYSIS OF THE PROCESS OF CREATIVE THINKING IN EDUCATION. *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*, 2(4).
12. Rahimjon o'g'li, A. A., & Adxam o'g'li, X. A. (2023). INKLYUZIV TA'LIM OLAYOTGAN BOLALARNI TAFAKKUR SOHASINI O'RGANISH.
13. Rahimjon o'g'li, A. A. (2022). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARDA MANTIQUIY TAFAKKUR RIVOJLANISHINING IJTIMOIIY PSIXOLOGIK MEXANIZMLARI. *SO 'NGI ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR NAZARIYASI*, 5(2), 116-119.

- 14.Rahimjon o‘g‘li, A. A., & Zafarjonovna, T. U. G. (2023). INFLUENCE OF TEMPERAMENT TYPES ON EDUCATIONAL EFFICIENCY. *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*, 2(11).